

LIQUEFACTION STUDY OF SUBSURFACE SOIL IN PART OF DELHI UNIVERSITY, NORTH CAMPUS

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ABSTRACT: Liquefaction and related phenomena have been responsible for tremendous amounts of damage in historical earthquakes around the world, especially in the cities built on young alluvial deposits. Delhi, the second most populated city of India is also one of the favorable sites for earthquake amplification with liquefiable younger alluvium. According to Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS 1893, Part 1:2002), Delhi falls in the high damage risk zone and can feel destruction up to MSK VIII (or MSK-64; Medvedev-Sponheuer-Karnik Scale). Though the city has a number of high rise buildings, it still continues to construct the high rise buildings and other mega structure, especially in the north campus area of the Delhi University. The present study is an attempt to evaluate the liquefiable subsurface soil in part of Delhi University North Campus. This study revealed that the average depth of liquefiable sub-surface soil in the study area is more than 8 meters. The study concluded that the area is highly susceptible to earthquake liquefaction and required appropriate mitigation to reduce the risk.

KEYWORDS: Liquefaction, PGA value, SPT N value, North Delhi

1. INTRODUCTION: Delhi is located within 28°24'17"N to 28°53'00"N latitudes and 76°50'24"E to 77°20'37"E longitudes and it falls in the seismic zone IV as per Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS 1893, Part 1:2002). Several earthquakes of magnitudes ranging from 3 to 7.4 have been observed in and around Delhi during the past three centuries. Moreover earthquake events which occurred in the Himalayan region, along the Main Boundary Thrusts (MBT) and Main Central Thrusts (MCT) have been felt in Delhi (1). Several earthquakes that occurred in and around NCR have injured or claimed lives in Delhi, e.g., October 10, 1956 (M 6.7), August 27, 1960 (M 6.0), August 15, 1966 (M 5.8) (2).

According to the census 2011, Delhi has a population of 1.67 crore, an increase from figure 1.39 crore in 2001 census. Due to rapid growth in population, urbanization has rapidly increased leading to rises in the number of high rise buildings, which is vulnerable to high seismic risk even due to moderate size earthquakes. Liquefaction induced ground failures, causes extensive structural and lifeline damage during an earthquake in urbanized areas around the world. Some examples of significant disaster caused by soil liquefaction due to earthquakes are 1964 Alaska Niigata, 1989 Loma Prieta, 1994 Northridge, 1995 Kobe and 1999 Izmit. In India, during the Bhuj great earthquake of 2001 ($M = 7.7$), several areas in Rann of Kutch had experienced liquefaction, sand and salt boil, and safer ground-cracking (3). The thickness of the quaternary alluvium soil cover of Delhi in both the eastern and western side of the ridge is variable from a few meters to about 300 meters. The eastern side of the ridge has thicker alluvium deposit covering larger area as compared to the western side. The young, loose and thick deposits of soil are more susceptible to liquefaction. Delhi has a typical geological set up, which can sustain large amplified shaking not only due to earthquakes in and around the region, but also due to strong earthquakes in the Himalayas (4). So, the necessary seismic factors should be taken into consideration for urban planning, industrialization, designing and construction of civil engineering structures. Therefore, it is very important to estimate an accurate earthquake liquefaction potential soil in Delhi area.

The University of Delhi, one of the most reputed universities in India with the student capacity of more than 5 lakhs approximately according to expressindia.com, 2008. Many high rise buildings and mega structure are developing in the north campus of Delhi University. On the other hand the area is highly susceptible to seismic and liquefaction hazards. The main objective of this paper is to estimate the depth of liquefiable subsurface soil in and around North Campus of Delhi University. In this study LiqIT software (Ver. 4.7.1) is used for liquefiable soil depth estimation by Boulanger and Idriss (5) method. The analyses will clarify the average depth of the liquefiable soil in the study area.

2. GEOLOGY OF DELHI: The rocks of Delhi belong both to the earliest and the latest chapters of the geological history of the earth: the Precambrian and the Quaternary [(6), (7)]. The intervening stratigraphic records are missing because the region has been lying exposed to sub-aerial erosion since it rose from beneath the sea in the late Precambrian times. The topography of the Delhi is generally flat except for a part known as a Delhi folds belt (DFB) in southern and central part of the area. The DFB seems to be a prolonged extension of the NNE-SSW trending Aravalli Mountain [(8), (9)].

Figure: I
 (a) Geology map of Delhi modified after Dubey et al. (27) and Bansal et al. (40).
 (b) Borehole location map.

Supergroup	Group	Litho-unit
Recent and sub-recent	Younger Alluvium (<10 Kyr)	Yamuna riverbed sand and other sediment deposits in the stream bed.
	Older Alluvium (>10 Kyr to ≈20 Kyr)	Small ferruginous sandy silt/clayey silt with kankar (calcareous concretions) beds
-----Unconformity -----		
Post Delhi Intrusive Delhi Super Group	Alwar Series (Precambrian)	Quartz veins and pegmatite Quartzite, grayish, bluish and pinkish in colour fine to coarse grained and thin inner beds of micaceous schist.
----- Base Unknown -----		

Table I: Geological Succession of Delhi area, modified after Mohanty et al., (41) and Dubey, (27).

The Precambrian rocks of the Delhi belong to the Alwar Series of the Delhi System [(10), (11)]. The Precambrian rock exposed in Delhi consists of quartzite interbedded with mica schist. The quartzites are gray to brownish gray, well bedded and highly jointed and structurally form a coaxially refolded regional antiform plunging southwest. The regional strike of the Alwar quartzite varies from NNE-SSW to NW-SE and the dip is of the order of about 35 to 80 degrees towards easterly and northeasterly direction.

The Alwar Series is unconformably overlain by alluvium sediments and windblown sands of the Quaternary period comprising older and newer alluvium. The younger alluvium also known as Khaddar, is riverine i.e., deposited by the Yamuna River [(12), (13)]. It is mainly consists of sand, silt and clay of varying proportions. The older alluvium, also known as Bhangar, constitutes mainly sandy silt particles that are deposited by the windblown sand from the nearby sandy regions of Rajasthan [(14), (15)].

The rock formation which is exposed in the north campus of Delhi Univeraity is mainly quartzite of the Alwar series of the Delhi Super group, unconformably overlain by the unconsolidated Quaternary to Recent sediments. The Quaternary sediments consist of older and newer alluvium. The older alluvium comprises of silt, sand and clay with kankar beds while the newer alluvium consists mainly of sand, silt and clay occurring in the older and active flood plains of the Yamuna River. The details geological successions of the area are shown in Table: 1.

3. SEISMICITY: Delhi and its surrounding region have a long seismic history being affected by several earthquakes from regional and local sources [(16), (17), (18), (19)]. The Himalayan thrust zone, just 200–250 km north of the megacity, has been identified as a significant seismic gap in the Central Himalayas [(20), (21)]. Several tectonic features such as the Himalayan Main Boundary Thrust (MBT) and the Main Central Thrust (MCT), the Delhi-Hardwar ridge, the Delhi-Lahore ridge, the Aravalli-Delhi fold, the Sohna fault, the Mathura fault, the Rajasthan Great Boundary Fault and the Moradabad fault in addition to several other minor lineaments, dominate this region. The tectonic activity in the region is found to be quite similar to the regions in other parts of the India like the Garhwal Himalayas, the Koyna region and the Northeast region (22), the Bhuj region (23), the NW Himalayan region (24) and the Kachchh Basin (25).

The first historically reported major earthquake in this region occurred on 15th July, 1720 having an intensity of IX (12). The significant earthquakes (magnitude above 5.5) that occurred in Delhi and adjoining areas are summarized in Table: 2

Earthquake Events and Dates	Epicenter locations	Magnitude and Areas
15th July, 1720	28.37° N-77.10° E	M = 6.5, Delhi
1st September, 1803	27.50° N-77.70° E	M = 6.8, Mathura
10th October, 1956	28.15° N-77.67° E	M = 6.7, Near Bulandshahar
27th August, 1960	28.20° N-77.40° E	M = 6.0, Near Faridabad
15th August, 1966	28.67° N-78.93° E	M = 5.8, Near Moradabad

Table II: Historical important earthquake events in and around Delhi, modified after Dasgupta et al. (42).

The Delhi area has revealed the maximum concentration of earthquake epicenters in (i) North-South trending Sonapat-Sohna fault, (ii) West of Delhi and (iii) at the tri-junction of Delhi-Haridwar ridge, Delhi–Lahore ridge and the axis of Delhi folding. It has been indicated that there are numerous hidden faults in the thick alluvial deposits of the Indo-Gangetic plains (26).

Recent studies by Dubey, et al. (27), discovered the presence of two major faults in the NW-SE direction by various techniques like Remote Sensing, GPR (Ground-PenetratingRadar) and Bouguer gravity anomaly analysis. First is a fault running through Faridabad-Mehrauli-Rohtak and the second aligned along Yamuna-Timarpur–Sonapat. They concluded that the possibility of finding more hidden faults beneath the Indo-Gangetic alluvium, sub-parallel to the regional strike of the Himalayan fault system and the revaluation of seismic zonation of the Delhi region from zone-IV to zone-V should be seriously considered.

4. LIQUEFACTION AND ITS EVALUATION METHOD: Liquefaction is a physical process which occurs during some earthquakes and it may lead to ground failure. The shaking causes increased pore water pressure which reduces the effective stress, and therefore reduces the shear strength of the sand. If there is a dry soil crust or impermeable cap, the excess water will sometimes come to the surface through cracks in the confining layer, bringing liquefied sand with it, creating sand boils, colloquially called “sand volcanoes” (28). The soil liquefaction depends on various factors such as the magnitude of earthquake; intensity and duration of ground motion; the distance from the source of the earthquake; site specific conditions; ground acceleration; type of soil and thickness of the soil deposit; soft; young; relative density; grain size distribution; fines content; plasticity of fines; degree of saturation; confining pressure; permeability characteristics of soil layer; position and fluctuations of the groundwater table; reduction of effective stress and shear modulus degradation [(29), (30), (31), (32),(33)].

Earthquake liquefaction is a major contributor to urban seismic risk. The liquefaction of soil had been observed for many years, but it was brought to the attention of engineers after Alaska Niigata, Japan in 1964. Seed and Idriss (34) first proposed a Simplified Procedure for evaluation of liquefaction. The procedure has evolved over time and is still being used worldwide to analyze liquefaction resistance of soil. Boulanger and Idriss (35) came up with another method for evaluating liquefaction, which is a modification of the well-established method by Seed and Idriss (34). The method is an update on the semi-empirical field-based procedures for evaluating liquefaction potential of cohesionless soils during earthquakes. This update includes recommended relations for each part of the analytical framework, including the: Stress reduction coefficient, Magnitude scaling factor, overburden correction factor for cyclic stress ratios, and overburden correction factor for penetration resistances. For each of these parameters, the emphasis was given on developing relations that capture the essential physics while being as simplified as possible. These updated relations were then used in re-evaluations of the field case histories derive revised deterministic SPT-based and CPT-based liquefaction correlations. Shear wave velocity based liquefaction correlations and the procedures for evaluating the cyclic loading behavior of plastic fine-grained soils have been dealt.

Seed & Idriss (34) discussed the modified methods of evaluation of liquefaction hazard and indicated that the method proposed by Boulanger and Idriss (5) should be used for estimation of liquefaction for Delhi soils. So, in this paper Boulanger and Idriss (5) method will be used for the evaluation of liquefaction depth in DU north campus.

5. METHODOLOGY: In this study we have collected 16 bore hole data in an around Delhi University North campus. To evaluate the depth of liquefiable soil, each and every borehole data has been calculated by using a software called ‘LiqIT ver. 4.7.1’ which has the capability of calculating the liquefiable depth of soil with different formulae developed by various scientists such as Boulanger and Idriss (5), Deterministic and Probabilistic methods of Seed etc. In this study we used Boulanger and Idriss (5) method for the estimation of liquefiable soil in part of DU north campus. The basic parameters used for estimation of liquefaction potential include depth wise SPT ‘N’ value and % fines along with PGA value and depth of ground water. The PGA values at surface were worked out by estimating shear wave velocity and soil amplification factor. In order to calculate the surface PGA values, the bedrock PGA map of Sharma (36) was used.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

6.1. SHEAR WAVE VELOCITY: Shear-wave velocity, [Vs] is an important parameter for evaluating the dynamic behavior of soil. Rao and Sathyam (37) carried out tests based on Multichannel Analysis of Surface waves (MASW) in Delhi at 118 sites in predefined grids of 2km x 3km each to estimate the shear-wave velocities. These tests were carried out using 48-channel digital seismograph and the collected data was analyzed using SeisImager/SW software. In addition, the average shear wave velocity up to 30m (Vs30) is estimated which is used for site characterization. The Vs30 for all the sites are calculated and it is ranging from 185 to 495 m/s in Delhi region. The regions like JNU, Vasant Kunj, Ladha Sarai, Nangloi Sayeid, that are in the southern part of Delhi has very high Vs30 (ranging from 450 to 500 m/s) because of shallow depths of rock outcrops. The locations falling in the North and East side has average shear wave velocity value less than 250 m/s and the locations in the western side of the area has values ranging from 250 to 350 m/s. The detailed site characterization based on the Vs30 is done by dividing the area into four zones ZA, ZB, ZC1 and ZC2. The study area falls both in Zone ZB and ZC1 which is shown in Figure 2. These zones are exactly matching with geology and soil characterization of the region. That is the zone ZA (Vs30 > 350 m/s) is falling in the Central and Southern part of Delhi where quartzite rock outcrops is available with dense gravely sands and the zone ZB (Vs30 = 250 to 350 m/s) is having dense sandy silts and silty sands with clean seams i.e. Pleistocene soils. The zones ZC1 and ZC2 (Vs30 < 250 m/s) are falling in the trans Yamuna region where soils are loose sandy silts with low SPT ‘N’ values (Holocene).

6.2. SOIL AMPLIFICATION FACTOR: Amplified site response at the soft soil sites can be obtained by using the Vs as an important geotechnical input parameter. The ratio between the actual time histories of the hard rock site to the amplified site response at the soft soil site gives the amplification factor. Sathyam (38) estimated the soil amplification factor (SAF) at various soil sites in Delhi and an amplification map is generated as shown in Figure 2.

The SAF is ranging from 1.03 (rocky sites) to 4.8 (soft soil sites) for Delhi region. The SAF is less than 1.2 for the locations falling in Zone ZA, 1.2 to 1.8 for ZB, 1.8 to 2.4 for ZC1 and greater than 2.4 for ZC2. Higher amplification values are observed in the trans Yamuna region and on the western side of Delhi because of high alluvial thickness. From this SAF map of Delhi, the study area is located in both Zone ZB and ZC1 which observed moderate to high amplification value.

Figure II: Seismic Microzonation Map of Delhi with Respect to Soil Amplification, after Sathyam, (28).

6.3. PEAK GROUND ACCELERATION IN DELHI REGION: Sharma (36) has computed peak ground acceleration (PGA) value at the bedrock for 20% exceedence values in 50 years within the Delhi region from six seismotectonic sources viz. Himalayan zone, Delhi-Hardwar Ridge zone, Moradabad fault zone, Great Boundary fault zone, Mathura fault zone and Sohna fault zone. The maximum PGA value of this region will experience a rise due to the combined effect of the six-seismotectonic zones. It indicates that southern part of Delhi is more affected by the Mathura fault while the western part has more PGA values due to Sohna fault. Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) contours as computed by Sharma et.al. (36) has been shown in figure 3(a).

In order calculate the PGA value of soil in Delhi area, the whole region is divided into small cells of 2.5' x 2.5' (approximately 4 km x 4 km). All these cells have been provided with a number Figure 3(b). The PGA value has been computed for each cell based on the area between two iso-acceleration contours Figure 3(c). Using the PGA values at the bedrock, the PGA values at the surface have then been computed by multiplying it with soil amplification factor (SAF) as discussed earlier. Figure 3(d) shows the surface PGA values as per this calculation. For all the boreholes falling within a particular cell, the PGA of the cell has been considered.

Figure III: (a): Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) Contours at Bed Rock (31).
 (b): Map of Delhi Area Divided Into Cells of 2.5' X 2.5'
 (c): PGA Values Computed at Bed Rock for Each Cell of 2.5' X 2.5' Using PGA Contours by Sharma (31).
 (d): PGA Values Computed at Surface for Each Cell of 2.5' X 2.5' Using PGA Values at Bed Rock and Soil Amplification Factor

6.4. ESTIMATION OF LIQUEFACTION POTENTIAL SOIL: The liquefaction potential depths of soil within all the boreholes were calculated using SPT ‘N’ values, percentage of fines and PGA value. The liquefaction was estimated using LiqIT v 4.7.1 (GEOLOGISMIKI Geotechnical Software) software using the following parameters:

Bore hole drilled depth	From collected borehole data
Percentage fines	Boulanger & Idriss (11) method
Depth of ground water table	From collected borehole data
SPT ‘N’ values at respective depths	Calculated based on Boulanger & Idriss (11) method
PGA value	Calculated based on the faults around Delhi by Sharma (2003) considering an earthquake of 6.5 magnitude

Table III: Important parameter used in calculating soil liquefaction.

Graphs between SPT ‘N’ values (N160) and estimated Cyclic Stress Ratio (CSR) were generated for each bore hole. A standard curve divides the graph in two parts – the points falling on the upper side of the curve represent the liquefiable thickness whereas the points on the other side represent the non-liquefiable soil were assessed. Figure 2(b) displays the graphs to assess the liquefaction depth for borehole no.70 near Vishwavidyalaya metro station.

Figure IV: (a) Curves relating CRR to (N1)60 published over the past 24 years for clean sands and the recommended curve for $M= 7\frac{1}{2}$ and $\sigma'_{vo}= 1 \text{ atm} (\approx 1 \text{ tsf})$. (b) Graphs between (N1)60 value and CSR

6.5. CROSS SECTION PROFILES: A cross section profile of the study area was prepared using 16 borehole data collected along the GTB Nagar Chowk to Vishwavidyalaya metro station. On the basis of the calculation done for CSR for each borehole and plotted it against the SPT N1 (60) values, the liquefaction depths arrived have been marked on each of the borehole. Figure 5 clearly shows the cross section profile showing the distribution of grain size classification (5a) and SPT N value (5b) of different borehole along the GTB Nagar Chowk to Vishwavidyalaya metro station with liquefiable soil.

The cross section profile of figure 5 (a) shows the distribution of grain size classification base on USCS (Unified Soil Classification System) along the metro line from GTB Nagar Chowk to Vishwavidyalaya metro station. The grain size analysis of the borehole shows that the whole cross section is dominated by sandy silt with some patches of clayey silt and silty sand deposit. The deposit of clayey silt occurs in three different locations, two of the deposits are found near GTB Nagar Chowk (< 200m in length) and another minor deposit occur between SGTB Khalsa college and Vishwavidhyalaya metro station (< 100m in length) whereas silty sand deposits originated near SGTB Khalsa college and extended upto Vishwavidhyalaya metro station (> 400 m in length). The type of the sediments, which are deposited in this area, is highly susceptible to earthquake liquefaction.

The standard penetration test (SPT) aims to determine the SPT N value, which gives an indication of the soil stiffness and it can be empirically related to many engineering properties (3). The SPT N value which is less than 30 is susceptible to liquefaction, Seed et al. (39). Based on field performance data, the corrected SPT N value distribution in this selected section is shown in figure 5 (b) and from this figure it can be concluded that the average depth of more than 13 m is highly vulnerable to subsidence and earthquake liquefaction.

Figure V: Cross section profile showing (a) grain size classification and (b) SPT N value distribution with Liquefiable soil.

Finally, the depths of the liquefaction soil were also estimated for each of the borehole using Boulanger and Idriss (5) method using LiqIT 4.7.1 software. The average depth of liquefiable soil is more than 8 meters, which are shown on figure 5. From this result, the selected area along GTB Nagar Chowk to Vishwavidyalaya metro station is in a High Liquefaction Hazard Zone.

7. CONCLUSION: In this study 16 borehole data in and around north campus of Delhi University were analyzed for estimation of the liquefiable depth of the soil. The average thickness of soil layer in the region is more than 30m. Boulanger and Idriss (5) method for liquefaction study was used in our study and it reveals that the average thickness of liquefiable soft soil in the study area is more than 8 meters. Any high-rise or mega building project will be susceptible to subsidence and liquefaction during a medium to major Earthquake in DU north campus area which lies in Seismic Zone IV.

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